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Integrating Sustainability Issues into a Comprehensive Architectural Design Studio: A Case Study Approach to the Development of a Framework

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ABSTRACT: To meet the performative goals of buildings, including energy efficiency, high indoor environmental quality, and occupant health and wellness, architectural design requires a collaborative process engaging various professionals including architects, engineers, and contractors. Successful collaboration in this process achieves high-performance building design, which may reduce the carbon footprint of the building. For training the coordinators of this collaborative process, typically building designers, comprehensive design has been emphasized in architectural education, and most architecture programs in the US offer a comprehensive design studio (CDS) as a mandatory course. The present study introduces three case studies on CDS teaching and attempts to identify the characteristics of a successful CDS with an emphasis on how sustainability issues could be integrated into the conventional comprehensive studio framework. The case studies included the relevant document analysis and communication with the instructors. The focuses of the investigated cases were building envelope systems, building performance, and building information modeling (BIM), and the common challenge was the limitation of time to address the broad study area. This indicates that students may need more opportunities for the application of knowledge to projects starting from the earlier stages of their education.

KEYWORDS: Comprehensive Design, Integrative Design, Sustainability, Architectural Education, Pedagogy

1. INTRODUCTION

Today, architects are being asked to design buildings for various performative goals including energy efficiency, high indoor environmental quality, and occupant health and wellness. To meet these goals in practice, architectural design is a collaborative process engaging various professionals including, among others, architects, engineers, and contractors. Typically, the architect leads the design development in communication with the project team members who are responsible for designing the various building systems. Through the education to be a designer and coordinator, it is essential to know how structure, enclosure, and multiple building systems interact and integrate into a building design.

The complexity of this endeavor is the reason comprehensive design has been emphasized in architectural education. Recently, there has been a concomitant interest in high-performance and sustainable design, which further emphasizes the need for a comprehensive approach. To promote the necessary knowledgebase, most architecture programs in the US offer a comprehensive design studio as a mandatory course. Although there has been a consensus about the need for a comprehensive design approach, there have been

few discussions on how the design studio should be defined and structured in architectural education to support the aforementioned goals.

The present study explored various comprehensive design studios offered in architecture programs in the US and conducted a comparative analysis. The research goal was to identify the characteristics of a successful comprehensive design studio and how the pedagogical model can be approached. To achieve this goal, three cases in different architecture programs were selected, and case studies, including the relevant document analysis and the communication with the instructors, were conducted. Emphasis was placed on how sustainability issues could be integrated into the conventional comprehensive studio framework.

2. BACKGROUND

Bovill, Gardner, and Wiedemann (1997) stated that architects are “rarely the maker of the built form,” and Comprehensive Design Studio (CDS) teaching demonstrates that “design does not end with the broad architectural idea” (p. 84). CDS shifts “the pedagogic focus, time and effort from schematic to design development” (Bermudez & Neiman, 2005, p. 176). Also, CDS provides students

with more critical exposure to the technical parameters and helps them utilize the information for their design iterations in the schematic design phase (Chung, 2014). Due to this specificity, the studies regarding CDS teaching have been published in the literature, particularly in journals and conferences regarding sustainable buildings and architectural education. Recently, with increasing concerns about climate change, there has been a trend to integrate various sustainability issues into the CDS framework.

Chung (2014) integrated building performance issues, that were previously taught in a building science lecture course, into his CDS framework. Applying the knowledge learned from the lecture to their own projects, students could test various types of building performance analyses as a meaningful design tool. In the case of Homer (2006), structural issues were integrated into the CDS framework in collaboration with the architectural engineering faculty and students. Criticizing the separation of “formalist architecture” and “rationalist architecture” in current education, the instructors of the studio emphasized the necessity of interdisciplinary education with more a holistic design approach (p. 1).

Ambrose (2009) and Stivers (2012) focused on building information modeling (BIM) as an educational platform for CDS education. Ambrose (2009) believed that BIM, which is based on “systems thinking and virtual simulations,” would be useful for teaching today’s CDS, and using BIM for CDS education would bring about a new way of thinking (p. 757). Similarly, Stivers (2012) introduced a team-taught CDS for a mixed student group from architecture and architectural engineering programs. In this studio, building information modeling (BIM) was employed as the studio design and communication platform due to its benefits for collaborative work.

While the aforementioned articles and papers presented specific study areas or tools, Haglund (2008) focused more on design competitions and grant opportunities as a part of the studio framework. He introduced two CDS studios, which used different design competitions, and compared the experiences to each other. He found that a more successful studio depended on the project selection, studio collaborators, and approach to the design issues as professionals. The studio projects won awards in various design competitions as well as a grant with an interdisciplinary team including the Bio-Regional Planning, Conservation, and Social Sciences departments (p. 3).

While the aforementioned articles and papers presented case-based studies, Bermudez and Neiman (2005) discussed the major challenges of

CDS teaching based on multiple CDS cases. They defined a CDS as “the academic environment that comes the closest to the practice of architectural design in an office” (Bermudez & Neiman, 2005, p. 172). Due to this environment that is typically managed by a team at an office with a full-time (or an extended) work schedule, CDS instructors and students tend to suffer from a lack of time that leads to underdeveloped projects and uneven learning outcomes. They suggested the following strategies as a solution: an intensive design workshop at the beginning of the semester, teamwork, curricular integration of the technical issues, critical ideology, and analog-digital media migration (Bermudez & Neiman, 2005, p. 174).

3. METHODOLOGY

The present study explored various comprehensive design studios offered in architecture programs in the US and conducted a comparative analysis. The research goal was to investigate the benefits and challenges of the comprehensive design studio (CDS) pedagogical models that introduced sustainability issues. To achieve this, three cases in different architecture programs were selected and analyzed based on the published articles about the courses and course materials. Emphasis was placed on how sustainability issues could be integrated into a conventional CDS framework.

3.1 Case study approach

A case study empirically investigates “a phenomenon or setting” within a real-world context (Groat & Wang, 2013, p. 418) and concentrates on “developing multifaceted analysis of a phenomenon” by using ‘thick description’ (Silverman & Patterson, 2014, p. 9). Even though a case study has a weakness in generalizability, it offers a “holistic view of a certain phenomenon or series of events” (Noor, 2008, p. 1603). Also, it shows “the embeddedness of the case in its context,” thus its real-life situation can be more compelling (Groat & Wang, 2013, p. 441).

3.2 Data collection and analysis

To select the cases, the literature on CDS teaching was thoroughly reviewed and categorized. Based on the literature review, three major issues in sustainability that were integrated into various design studios were identified: building envelope systems, building performance, and the integration of building information modeling (BIM). One case from each of the three categories, was selected for further investigation. One of the important criteria for selecting the cases was the ease of data collection, including the syllabus, assignment briefs,

and student work. The collected data were categorized and compared with each other to understand the commonalities and differences.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The common challenges of the selected cases were managing the limited time and finding the balance between creativity and technology. The common benefits of the studios were as previously described in the literature: the “insightful balance between theory and practice” (Bermudez & Neiman, 2005, p. 176) and the bridge between academia and professional practice (Bovill et al., 1997; Stivers, 2012). The following sections summarize further details of each case.

4.1 Building envelope systems

In Case A, the studio was composed of the two following design phases. In Phase 1, students designed a High School Center for the Performing Arts based on a given building program. They developed and represented the design ideas with architectural drawings that included site plans, floor plans, elevations, sections, and models. In Phase 2, building envelope systems were specifically highlighted, which required wall sections and section details of the building that students developed in Phase 1. Each phase was connected to a different design competition, and students had an option to submit their proposals to the competition at the end of each phase. The first competition was organized by an association specializing in space design for education, and the second competition was organized by an association with expertise in building envelope systems.

Figure 1:
Preliminary sketches of the floor plans and building sections ©Jacklynn Benfield

Professionals from the associations were invited to the studio reviews and supported the students’ idea development. Figure 1 demonstrates a student project developed in Phase 1.

Within the aforementioned framework, students studied, discussed, and presented the following areas of their building design in the studio throughout the semester:

1. Project thesis—the central ideas of the design approach
2. Pre-design—interaction with the building program
3. Site design - responses to contextual and physical site characteristics
4. Codes and regulations – responses to relevant codes and regulations including the principles of life-safety and accessibility standards
5. Structural systems – principles of structural systems including their ability to withstand gravitational, seismic, and lateral forces, how the selected structural systems support the design thesis and express the underlying ideas
6. Environmental systems – how the environmental systems integrate with the aesthetic qualities of the design, address building orientation, employ passive and active strategies for thermal comfort and indoor air quality, provide good-quality lighting, and address acoustical concerns
7. Building envelope systems and assemblies – building envelope systems and how the systems address the aesthetics, moisture transfer, durability, energy, and material resources
8. Building service systems - lighting, mechanical, plumbing, electrical, communication, vertical transportation, security, and fire protection systems

While these areas followed the typical requirements in a CDS, the specific focus on the building envelope in Phase 2 with the involvement of building envelope experts was a distinguishing part of this studio, which enabled more in-depth learning about building envelope systems and details. Through conversations with the experts, students gained a better understanding of their building skins and how technical issues affect the design. Figure 2 shows a wall section drawn by a student in the second phase.

Figure 2:
Wall sections ©Jacklynn Benfield

4.2 Building performance

Case B was a team-taught graduate-level CDS that focused on low-energy housing projects. Considering the transition of the architectural design trend from an “aesthetic and assembly-oriented trajectory” to a “comprehensive understanding of the relationship between design thinking and building performance” under the goal of sustainable design, this studio addressed the building performance issues in collaboration with the Master of Science in High- Performance Building program (Gamble, Gentry, Augenbroe, & Technology, 2015, p. 68). Utilizing design competitions as a driver of the project, the studio consisted of the following stages (Gamble & Rakha, 2019):

1. Body, Space, and Systems Ideation – focusing on space programming/planning and building systems
2. Body, Enclosure, and Site Ideation - focusing on the site analysis/planning and building envelope
3. 2 Family Prototype Aggregate - development of scalable 2-family domestic prototype
4. Multi-scale Family Prototype Aggregate – development of multi-family domestic prototype

Following this structure, the Master of Architecture students had weekly meetings with the Master of Science students who served as their building performance consultants. In the meetings, various technical issues were discussed in-depth, and building performance analyses were applied to students’ projects. The students collaborated for building performance simulations of the project using various simulation tools that can be plugged into Autodesk or Rhino/Grasshopper software. Conducting the building performance simulations from the early stages of design allowed the students to develop more environment-responsive design ideas and broaden the topics of their applied research. Through the meetings and simulations, the environmental impacts of the proposed passive and active design strategies were tested. A specific focus was technically “provable” parts of the building’s performance including the energy use and the greenhouse gas emissions of the project (Gamble et al., 2015). Figure 3 shows one of the lighting performance studies conducted by a student team during the studio.

Figure 3:
Lighting performance simulations © www.zedhstudio.com

In addition to the collaborations among the students, the dissemination of the design outcomes and the connection with various industrial partners were also a remarkable part of the studio. The industrial partners, encompassing human-scale furniture, building-scale performance issues, and community-scale sustainability, sponsored the studio and served as external critics for the studio reviews. Moreover, the student work and the studio activities were published on the studio website each

semester, which helped students stay motivated and expose their work to the public. These efforts to communicate with a third party, such as sponsors and public, became an effective way of gaining a fresh perspective and spreading the vision of the studio about sustainable architecture to the realm outside academia. Although the collaborations primarily concentrated on the incorporation of building physics and energy-efficient design technologies into the studio, such as construction methods and innovative building materials, the instructors acknowledge that urban-scale issues should be a key part of the project as well, which may prompt more community engagement and debates on sustainable housing in “urban areas with increasing density” (Gamble et al., 2015, p. 85). Figure 4 shows one of the outcomes of this studio.

Figure 4: Beltline bike hotel project © Gabriella Melendez

4.3 Integration of BIM

In Case C, Building Information Modeling (BIM) was employed as the design idea development and assembly platform for the studio’s “systems thinking” approach proposed by Meadows (2008). A system refers to an “interconnected set of elements that is coherently organized in a way that achieves something” and is composed of “elements, interconnections, and a function or purpose” (Meadows, 2008, p. 11). The studio framework emphasized these three components that can be translated into Adaptive Assemblies, building programs, and site information in architectural projects. Adaptive Assemblies in this studio was an exercise to develop three main structure and building envelope systems, a porous wall, a retaining wall, and a green roof assembly, that show the building materials and key factors responding to the site condition and building program (Palagi, 2019).

Different from the conventional building design process, which typically progresses from large-scale volume studies to small-scale section studies, this studio required the project to begin with an Adaptive Assemblies exercise that included section detail studies. This reversed approach allowed the students to explore the materiality of the buildings and human-scale experiences first, which could become a logic for creating a building form. With this approach, students could read their project as a system rather than an aesthetic object. The axonometric studies in the second stage connected the microscale studies with the macroscale circulation and spatial adjacencies. The process of this transition from microscale to macroscale is illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Process of translation between the two methods of investigations – Adaptive Assembly and Axonometric studies © A. Verastegui, Kris Palagi

The primary platform for these investigations was the parametric modeling environment in Revit, the most popular building information modeling (BIM) software. Since more and more architects and engineers utilize BIM in the industry, students could be prepared for their future collaborations with this opportunity of using a BIM platform for their projects. Furthermore, the parametric function of the tool and the embedded information on the materials and structural members supported students’ systematic and multidisciplinary thinking. Stivers (2012) mentioned that the real-time “quantitative and qualitative feedback” that designers receive from BIM can justify the concept “beyond its subjective functional or aesthetic qualities,” and this interaction ultimately impacts the designers’ thinking processes. Despite the benefits of using BIM in the studio framework, the instructors found that the application of BIM was more challenging for students than professionals, specifically due to the limited time and the difficulty in finding a balance between critical thinking and automated design.

Landscape, community, and social equity issues were also addressed in Case C. In collaboration with a landscape design/civil engineering studio, this studio proposed a pavilion for a community farm that could be an architectural solution to the food desert problem in the project site area. The regular meetings with landscape and civil engineering student groups throughout the semester gave students an opportunity for interdisciplinary thinking and integrating community issues into an architectural project. However, time management was the challenging part of the studio, specifically with the gap between the community and the building scales. Figure 6 shows a student project in Case C, which proposed an Urban Food Hub Distribution Center.

Figure 6: Urban Food Hub Distribution Center © Dylan Roth

5. CONCLUSION

The present study investigated different types of CDS education and identified the common challenges and benefits of integrating sustainability issues into comprehensive design studios. CDS generally occurs at the end of an architectural education, and students have an opportunity to apply the knowledge learned in lecture courses to their projects (Stivers, 2012). The studio’s duration was insufficient to accomplish work reaching the level of design development, in part owing to students’ lack of knowledge and experience. Considering that this was the most challenging part of the studio teaching in all cases, students may need to have more opportunities for the application of knowledge to their projects starting from the earlier stages of their education. Despite the challenges, all the investigated cases were successful enough to win awards in various design competitions and give students an opportunity to face a broader audience outside their programs. The limitation of the present study may be the number of investigated cases, which may not be sufficient to generalize the findings. Therefore, future studies may be expanded to additional cases and can be a catalyst for further discussions among architectural researchers, educators, and professionals.

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